

COMMUNICATIVE ABILITIES , CHARACTER, AND ACTION AS A UNIT OF HUMAN ACTIVITY

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Abstract: The article provides argumentation of communicative abilities, argumentation of character, in human activity. The system of relations expresses the content of the character, its individual originality. The structure of characterological relationships consists mainly of a person's relationship to his business and work, to people around him, as well as to himself.

Keywords: communicative abilities, character, abilities, will, activity

Communication skills are the ability to engage in communication and establish business contacts, connections, relationships. As a rule, in everyday life we used to call it in one word – sociability. Communication is a type of activity that has its own laws, consists of successive stages and, therefore, requires certain skills. Communicative abilities are abilities that include knowledge, skills and abilities related to communication and interaction with other people, interpersonal assessment and perception, establishing contacts, establishing connections, finding a common language, self-esteem and influencing people.

Subject-activity abilities are the abilities that determine the interaction of people with inanimate objects.

All kinds of abilities are complementary, and it is their combination that gives a person the opportunity to develop most fully and harmoniously. Abilities have an impact both on each other and on a person's success in life, activity and communication.

Character is a holistic personality formation that determines the characteristics of human activity and behavior and is characterized by a stable attitude to various aspects of activity.

The character expresses the most typical, essential features of a person, the knowledge of which allows to some extent to foresee how a person will act in certain cases. The formation of character takes place in the conditions of the inclusion of the individual in various social groups (family, friendly companies, labor or educational team, etc.). The character is determined by the social existence of the individual, the assimilation of social experience, the formation of a certain system of human relations to reality and to himself. Typical character traits are determined by the typical circumstances of a person's life path in specific historical conditions.

an individual, which express the ways of his behavior and ways of emotional response. Translated from Greek, "character" means "seal", "coinage". The expression "it is characteristic of him" means that certain actions and actions of a person are typical for him, natural. The character of a person seems to leave a certain imprint on his behavior and relationships with other people. The character concentrates the most pronounced, the most essential features of a person as a subject of activity, communication, cognition.

Character, however, does not include all the stable properties that stand out and are fixed in a person. It includes only those properties that express a person's attitude to the main aspects of life and activity. Character is manifested in what a person does and in how he does it, i.e. character can be expressed both in content and in the form of behavior.

When assessments of the character and personality of the same person are given, these assessments may not only not coincide, but also be opposite in sign: a person may be an outstanding person with a rather complex or bad character.

Personality traits are usually divided into motivational and instrumental. Motivational ones encourage, direct and support the activity, while instrumental ones give it a certain style. Character refers to the instrumental sphere of personality. It is no longer the content that depends on it, but the manner of performing the activity. However, it should be borne in mind that there is no clear

boundary between the motivational and instrumental spheres. Character can also manifest itself in the choice of the goal of action, but when the goal is defined, character acts more as a means to achieve the goal, i.e. in his instrumental role.

Thus, we can say that character traits reflect how a person acts, and personality traits reflect what he acts for. The ways of behavior and the orientation of the personality are relatively independent: you can achieve different goals using the same methods, and vice versa, achieve the same goal in different ways.

Character, like temperament, reveals dependence on the physiological characteristics of a person, and above all on the type of nervous system. The properties of temperament leave their imprint on the formation of character, determining the dynamic features of its occurrence, i.e. temperament, represents the dynamic side of character. Features of temperament can counteract or contribute to the development of certain characterological traits.

Character is a lifelong acquisition of personality, it accumulates human habits and is largely the result of self—education. Temperament does not unilaterally and definitively determine the path of development of specific character traits, temperament itself is transformed within certain limits under the influence of character properties. The development of character and temperament in this sense are mutually dependent processes. In character, personality is revealed from the side of its content, in temperament — from the side of dynamic manifestations.

Character is not a simple aggregate, a random set of isolated traits. It is a complex mental education consisting of a system of numerous stable personality traits that express a person's attitude to the world around him, work, other people and himself. These relationships are fixed in the forms of behavior, activity and communication that are familiar to a person. Natural relationships between individual character traits express its structurality. The structurality of the character allows, knowing this or that trait, to assume that this person has a number of other traits.

The structurality of the character is also expressed in a certain hierarchy of its features. This means that among the character traits, some are the main, defining and leading, while others are secondary, less significant. The main, leading, features to one degree or another subordinate the secondary, less significant ones, causing their varying degrees of manifestation in certain situations.

The system of relations expresses the content of the character, its individual originality. The structure of characterological relationships consists mainly of a person's relationship to his business and work, to people around him, as well as to himself.

- In relation to their activities, work, such character traits as diligence or laziness, neatness or negligence, a sense of novelty or conservatism, enthusiasm or a formal attitude to work may manifest themselves.
- In interpersonal relationships, sociability or isolation of a person, collectivism or individualism, politeness or rudeness, truthfulness or falsehood, etc. are manifested.
- In relation to a person to himself, high demands or complacency, self-criticism or exaggerated self-conceit, modesty or arrogance, self-esteem or underestimation are indicative of the character. In addition, there are character traits related to the peculiarities of the cognitive, emotional and volitional spheres of a person.
- Cognitive character traits include a mindset (theoretical or practical) and qualities of mind (analyticity, criticality, flexibility, etc.).
- Emotional character traits include passion, sentimentality, as well as traits based on moral feelings: patriotism, humanity, etc.
- In strong-willed character traits (determination, endurance, perseverance, courage, etc.), the attitude to obstacles finds expression. Strong-willed character traits cannot be evaluated without taking into account the orientation of the personality. They are valuable only if there is a morally educated will aimed at achieving socially useful goals. Strong-willed traits are sometimes called the

"backbone" of character and, depending on their development, the character is attributed to a strong or weak type. The strong character of the person who always acts according to his beliefs, consistently behaves in various, including difficult, conditions, shows perseverance in achieving his goals. Weakness of character manifests itself in inconsistency of behavior, in discrepancies between words and deeds, in fear of difficulties.

It is important to identify its stability or instability when assessing its character. A person with a stable character retains his inherent attitudes, beliefs, habits and other characteristics for a long time. With an unstable character, views, beliefs and attitudes change quickly.

The system of relations that make up the structure of character, in some cases, has the quality of integrity, in others — inconsistency. The integral character of the person whose individual thoughts, feelings, views, actions are consistent with each other, correspond to his beliefs. Conviction determines a person's principled behavior, confidence in justice and the importance of the cause to which he gives all his strength. A person with a contradictory (disharmonious) character is distinguished by the presence of incompatible views and beliefs, goals and motives, aspirations, desires and actions.

Character is a very complex education. In real life, there are many shades in the characters of people, transitions between different polar features of character properties, which explains the infinite variety of characters, the dissimilarity of people from each other.

An important characteristic of a person is also her abilities — individual psychological characteristics that determine the success of an activity or a number of activities, irreducible to knowledge, skills and abilities, which determine the ease and speed of learning new ways and techniques of activity.

B.M.Teplov proposed to separate the makings and abilities. At the same time, the makings are defined by the researcher as innate, physiological characteristics of a person, which serve as a natural basis for the development of

abilities. They are conditions for the development of abilities, but they do not predetermine giftedness. In the process of mental development of the personality, the makings are transformed and changed.

Several criteria are used to classify abilities.

1. According to the criterion of the type of mental functional systems, abilities are divided into:

- o sensorimotor;
- o perceptual;
- o attentional;
- o mnemonic;
- o thinking;
- o communicative;

2. According to the criterion of the main type of activity on:

- o scientific (mathematical, linguistic, etc.);
- o creative (musical, literary. artistic);
- o engineering, etc

3. In addition, distinguish between general and special abilities. General abilities are associated with the performance of leading forms of human activity, and special abilities are associated with individual activities. Among the general abilities, most researchers distinguish general intelligence, creativity (general ability to create) and, less often, learning ability.

The results of psychogenetic studies indicate a high level of heritability of general intelligence and some special abilities (in particular, mathematical, musical). Meanwhile, creativity is more dependent on the influence of the social microenvironment. A high level of development of general (special) abilities is characterized as general or special giftedness, or talent.

The highest degree of development of the individual's abilities, expressed in creativity, which is of outstanding importance for the life of society, is genius. Genius is characterized by extreme creative productivity, mastering the cultural

heritage of the past and at the same time resolutely overcoming outdated norms and traditions. A brilliant personality contributes to the progressive development of society through his creative activity.

Psychological studies have shown that based on the early diagnosis of general abilities, it is possible to give a probabilistic forecast of the success of a person's social and professional career.

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